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Case Study

Congenital Aganglionic Megacolon”: A Rare Case Report of Hirschsprung Disease with Recurrent Surgical Complications

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ABSTRACT

An uncommon congenital disorder known as Hirschsprung disease (HSCR) affects roughly 1 in 5,000 live infants. It occurs when ganglion cells are absent in the colon, leading to an obstruction in the gut. This case study focuses on an 8-years old girl diagnosed with a history of HSCR, previously underwent stage-1 re-section during her neonatal period and a Leveling colostomy on November 2023, due to severe bowel obstruction. On May 2024, she presented with multiple complications, including abdominal distension, intermittent fever, respiratory distress, pedal edema, and underwent stage-II Soave pull-through surgery. Despite intensive management, unfortunately, she experienced persistent fever, electrolyte imbalance and pleural effusion. After seven months, she returned with symptoms of a colonic-leak, Disseminated Intravascular coagulation (DIC), abdominal rupture, sepsis and non-healing abdominal wound while on ileostomy. A post-colon closure scan indicated mild bowel wall edema with persistent leukocytes, suggesting ongoing inflammation. This case highlights the challenges and complexities of post-operative care in pediatric patients with HSCR. Treatment included laparotomy, ileostomy, and secondary suturing to address these complications.

INTRODUCTION

Disorders that occur as a result of faulty neural crest cell formation are known as neurocristopathies. One of such disorders is

Hirschsprung Disease (HSCR), or congenital mega colon, or intestinal aganlionosis.[1] Its global range incidence is from 1 per 2,000 live births, but the most frequently reported incidence rate is 1 per 4,000 live births. [2] It may be

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associated with various gene mutations like RET, GDNF, EDNRB, SOX10, and PHOX2B, among others. [3] HSCR is a congenital disease characterized by the lack of ganglion cells at Meissner's plexus of the submucosa and Auerbach's plexus of muscularis. [4] Also referred to as congenital aganglionic mega colon. [5] It is caused by the failure of enteric neural crest cells to complete their craniocaudal migration to the gut wall early in embryogenesis. [6] It largely involves males, with a ratio of male-to-female = 4:1. [7] HSCR is an uncommon congenital disease largely involving newborns and pediatrics. This condition can lead to functional bowel obstruction in the form of megacolon, chronic constipation, recurrent colitis, or a potentially life-threatening risk of perforation. [8] The contrast enema is the initial diagnostic procedure of choice. It well demarcated the transition zone between the narrow aganglionic bowel and dilated normal bowel. A rectal biopsy is another essential diagnostic test that demonstrates the absence of ganglion cells in the intestinal wall. [9] Despite the fact that some of the colon without nerve cells is cut out in an operation to correct HSCR, several extra mucosal colonic biopsies and initial diversion in the type of a colostomy are usually necessary before definitive surgery can be undertaken. [10] Having a colostomy severely affects one's quality of life. [11] The most commonly performed procedures for HSCR are Duhamel retro rectal pull-through, Soave endorectal pull-through modified and full thickness Swenson pull-through. Obstructive symptoms post-operatively are one of the most frequent complications. [12] Peinold et al. found early physiotherapy beneficial in decreasing post-operative complications and avoiding failure in abdominal surgery. We identified significant obstructive symptoms in our own case study. The main goal of this case was to present an overview of the HSCR phenotype, diagnosis, and treatment options; discuss the primary genetic causes and

how they disrupt normal enteric neural crest cell development; and explore new pathways that may contribute to the pathophysiology of HSCR. Early physiotherapy intervention is important in decreasing complications following surgery and avoiding failure of abdominal surgery.

CASE PRESENTATION:

An 8-year-old girl with a history of chronic constipation, otherwise healthy at birth, was diagnosed with Hirschsprung disease (HSCR) in November 2023 at Santhiram General Hospital. She was born vaginally at term without any significant neonatal complications. [13] During the neonatal period the patient had stage-1 surgery, where the diseased bowel was removed. On November 14, 2023, a leveling colostomy was done to decompress a severe HSCR-induced bowel obstruction. She had symptoms of intermittent fever, mild pedal edema, abdominal pain localized to the right lower quadrant and loose stools in May 2024. Abdominal imaging showed fluid-filled, edematous loops of the bowel, mild fat stranding in the hypogastrium on the left, and minimal right pleural effusion. The recto-sigmoid resection pathology report confirmed the lack of ganglionic cells, which is typical of HSCR. A barium enema contrast study showed a narrowed distal segment and a dilated proximal colon, which confirmed the diagnosis. Acute intestinal obstruction and fecal peritonitis were diagnosed in the patient. An in-situ ileostomy with a drain was established on May-1, 2023. After the ileostomy, the child had two episodes of bilious vomiting and an increasing fever. On May-6, 2024, Soave's pull-through procedure was performed as two-stage pull-through procedure (TERPT). [14] During the post-operative course, the patient had a dehiscence of the abdominal wound with puss drainage, which required consultation with a plastic surgeon. Additional investigation showed disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC),

fecal peritonitis, right lower lobe consolidation, and mild pleural effusion. Therefore, debridement of the abdomen was done [15] Seven months after that, the patient presented with evidence of a colonic leak and an open wound in the abdomen,

even though she was on ileostomy. The leak was diagnosed as closed colonic leak, and the abdomen and flap grafting were repaired. [16] A chronological sequence of these events is given in **Table 1.**

Occurrence of Events	Dates of Events
Diagnosis of Hirschsprung disease	November 2023
Leveling colostomy	14 th of November 2023
Stage-II S/P Laparotomy pull-through of HSCR	6 th of May 2024
PICU admission for recurrent vomiting and abdominal distension.	11 th May 2024
Ileostomy with drain in-situ due to fecal peritonitis	14 th of May 2024
Closure of colonic-leak, abdomen, & flap grafting	6 th of December 2024

CASE DISCUSSION:

This 8-year-old female patient with a history of Hirschsprung disease, a congenital condition due to abdominal migration of the neural crest cells, presented with bilious vomiting and focal abdominal pain. She had a history of leveling colostomy and bowl resection for HSR with chronic constipation. On she was found to have tachycardia (PR: 52CPM), dehydration (dry oral mucosa), stupor, and hypotension (BP: 100/50), and an abdominal low blood glucose level (GRBS: 52 mg/dl), indicative of sepsis or metabolic dearrangement. Her body temperature was 100.5⁰C. A Systemic examination revealed abdominal tenderness, crisp breathe sounds (RS: BAE+), and normal heart sounds (CVS S1S2+), but normal neurological tone in plantar flexors. Microscopic findings confirmed aganglionic segments in the rectum, sigmoid colon, and anastomic regions. Contrast enema X-ray demonstrated the characteristic dilated proximal

colon and narrowed distal segment, indicative of functional obstruction, an abnormal recto-sigmoid ratio with a short rectum, in favor of HSCR. Abdominal and chest ultrasound revealed fluid-filled edematous bowel loops, mild fat stranding, and minimal right pleural effusion. Management included a combination of broad-spectrum antibiotics (Meropenem 1 gm. IV TID, Piperacillin-Tazobactam 1.6 gm. IV BD, Metronidazole 350 mg TID), proton pump inhibitors (Pantoprazole 20 mg IV BD), and analgesics (Tramadol 25 mg IV in 500 ml NS, Ketorolac 1 cc in 4 ml NS SOS) for analgesia, Vitamin C (Limcee 500 mg IV OD), Faropenem (200 mg TID), Zincovit syrup (5 ml OD), and Taxim (40 mg/kg BD) for immunity building and prevention of infection. Paracetamol (Dolo 650 mg, 1/2-tab SOS) was prescribed to control pain and fever. This comprehensive treatment regimen addressed the patient's infection risk, metabolic disturbances, and pain, with appropriate observation.

Table 2. Abnormal Lab investigation seen in Patient.

Parameter	Result values	Biological references
Complete Blood Picture		
Hemoglobin	10.8	12-14 gm/dl
T.W.B.C	13,700	4,000-11,000/cmm
Polymorphs	76	50-70%

Lymphocytes	11	25-45%
T.R.B.C	2.5	4.5-5.5 millions/cmm
M.C. V	82	86-98 FL
M.C.H	26	27-32 pg.
Platelet count	6.71	1.5-4 lakh/cmm
ESR	30	0-15 mm/hr.
Liver Function Test		
Albumin	2.7	2.5-5 gm/dl
Total Proteins	4.8	6.0-8.3 gm/dl
Serum Electrolytes		
Chlorides	108	96-106 mmol/l
Calcium	7.7	8.5-10.2 mg/dl
Peripheral Smear:		
Normocytic and Normochromic Anemia with Thrombocytopenia.		

Figure-1

Figure-2

Figure: No: 1. Contrast Enema X-ray showing colonic dilation narrowed aganglionic segment (Indicated by the red arrow).

This contrast enema X-ray shows a clear difference between the dilated proximal colon and the narrower distal segment. This indicates a functional obstruction due to aganglionosis and highly suggests the Hirschsprung disease.

This illustrates the patient with colonic dilation and demonstrating transition zone. The abnormal colonic motility is evidenced by the abrupt change in diameter and delayed evacuation of the contrast material. The aganglionic segment stays tightly contracted, blocking stool flow and showing the stretched, enlarged mega colon above the blockage. And also highlights the thin, non-functional bowel segment lacking nerve cells

Figure: No: 2. Contrast Enema X-ray demonstrating Transition Zone (indicated by the red arrow).

Figure-3

Figure: No: 3. Contrast Enema X-ray Demonstrating Lower Abdominal Contrast Distribution and Potential Obstruction.

Illustrates an abnormal recto-sigmoid ratio due to the rectum being shorter than the sigmoid colon. Image 2 (top-right): Indicated by the red arrow highlights the transition zone which is the hallmark of Hirschsprung disease. The aganglionic segment stays tightly contracted, blocking stool flow. Image 3 (bottom-left): Indicated by yellow

arrow showing the stretched, enlarged mega-colon above the blockage. Image 4 (bottom-right): Indicated by blue arrow highlights the thin, non-functional bowel segment lacking nerve cells (aganglionic segment).

After the Surgery:

Figure-4.

Usg Of Abdomen and Chest:

After performing a review for post-operative scan of abdomen revealed fluid filled edematous bowel loops noted, mild fat stranding noted, hypogastrium toward left side and the minimal right pleural effusion. Interdisciplinary approaches are crucial for managing the risks and achieving optimal patient outcomes. The prescribed medications involved Antibiotics, Antipyretics, and vitamin supplements

CONCLUSION:

This case illustrates the significant challenges of treating Hirschsprung disease, particularly when complicated by severe post-operative issues. Despite a carefully planned surgical intervention, the patient faced critical complications, including sepsis, disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), and fecal peritonitis. To stabilize the patient's condition, these life-threatening complications need immediate, forceful surgical and medical management. The fact that successful control of these fatal complications is possible underscores the significance of early and correct diagnosis, timely surgical intervention decision, and aggressive sepsis control measures. The present case underscores the importance of long-term follow-up and coordination of an organized multidisciplinary healthcare team in addressing the problem of compromised wound healing and prevents future morbidity; the present case highlights the importance of long-term follow-up and coordination of an organized multidisciplinary health care team. Ultimately, this case serves as a profound reminder of vital need for individualized and adaptable management approaches in the field of pediatric surgery, ensuring that each patient's unique needs are met effectively.

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